

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)
Milestone 11 – QST Monitoring Framework Set Up
Internal Report

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1 Purpose of the document:

This document is to set out the approach to monitoring and evaluating the implementation of Quantitative Story Telling (QST) during Hutton C3 (Scottish Land Use Transformations) project 2022-2027.

This forms part of C3.4 “Scientific and wider societal exploitation of research outputs” with the focus on monitoring and evaluating the process of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary working.

It represents the fulfilment of Milestone 11 (QST monitoring framework set up) due by end of Q1 (June 2022).

The approach will be used to monitor the 1st QST cycle starting in July 2022 and running to March 2023. The guidance will be a living document and updated if necessary.

2 WHY Monitor & Evaluate (M&E)

The reason to monitor and evaluate the process of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary working within the QST cycles is twofold:

- To learn what did and did not work with the aim of improving the QST methodology;
- To assess the different forms of impact achieved using the QST methodology;
- To identify and evidence ‘good practice’ in relation to carrying out QST

The rationale for the approach to M&E is provided in Annex 1. It positions knowledge as relational, multiple dimensional and contextual. It is utility-focussed – highlighting learning in order to improve both processes and outcomes of science-policy interactions. The approach is formative (learning during the implementation process) and qualitative (based on making sense of varied text-based data and not seeking statistically significant correlations).

3 WHAT to M&E

The part identifies the main elements to monitor to undertake an evaluation. In each round of QST, the evaluation process should consider:

- What is the focus of the QST?
- What is the desired impact(s)¹ the QST is seeking?
- Who is involved in the QST (and at which stages) and how were they selected?
- What role(s) does each person play and do these roles change over time?
- What choices are made at each stage?
- Why were these choices made? By whom?
- What happens during each stage of the cycle?
- What types of impacts occur by the end of the cycle?
- What do participants feel they learnt?
- What do they feel contributes towards the outcome of the QST?

¹ Awareness raising; connectivity; capacity building; conceptual; instrumental

4 HOW to M&E

4.1 Data Sources:

The qualitative data to answer the evaluation questions will be contained in mainly secondary sources but will include some primary data collected purposively for the M&E process.

Secondary data will mainly be the QST meeting notes (internal working documents not publicly available) and supporting video/voice recording files. These data will include any workshops conducted as part of the first and last stages of QST. Relevant emails exchanged about the process or outcomes of QST will also be used.

Primary data will be any feedback forms or questionnaires used as part of a workshop process as well as interviews with participants at the end of the QST cycle by researchers not involved in the QST process itself but part of the Hutton C3 social research team.

All data will be used anonymously where possible and in compliance with the principles outlined within the approved Hutton social research ethics submission #27/2022. Where anonymity is not possible, the potentially identifiable participant will be notified and given the opportunity to check a draft prior to publication.

4.2 Data Management:

The M&E team will keep an excel spreadsheet of data sources for each stage of the QST cycle. There will be a tab that helps us track the different actors involved in QST (both within the Hutton team and other participants). This will be checked quarterly to ensure that the relevant data are available for evaluation.

The relevant data sources (word files, excel rows or columns) will be imported into NVIVO software. A combination of cases, attributes and nodes will be used to allow the data to be searched by QST cycle, stage of cycle, participants and other criteria (such as organisation or discipline).

4.3 Data Analysis:

The data within the NVIVO database will be thematically analysed using the questions within the “What to M&E” section. The draft findings and their implications for further QST cycles will be discussed with the QST team before they are finalised.

5 WHEN to M&E

As implied above, M&E will be undertaken throughout each QST cycle, with the main outcomes and lessons learnt considered at the end of each cycle. Formative evaluation implies continuous reflection and learning, so it will be possible to make changes during a QST cycle rather than waiting until after it has finished.

6 FOR WHOM is the M&E useful:

Utility focussed M&E is designed to support improved science-policy interactions. Therefore M&E is being undertaken for these users:

- For QST participants to understand the impact of QST on their own practices
- For Hutton researchers to improve the QST methodology in future iterations
- For other potential users of QST in other settings

7 Format of evaluation

Word document explaining what has been learnt and recommendations for the next round of QST primarily to inform how to plan to the next round of QST; and supplementary products (e.g. 1 page summary) for an external policy audience; and slightly longer summary of what QST achieved for external academic audience (5 pages). Working on 1:5:25 rule.

Annex 1 Background on methods and approaches

Similar to the post-normal science that forms the foundations of QST (Saltelli & Giampietro, 2017), the underlying approach to M&E within this research is the view that knowledge is relational. The research aims to move away from modernist approaches to evaluation that have been prevalent in M&E, and which research has highlighted to hinder the M&E process (K. A. Waylen & Blackstock, 2017; K. A. Waylen et al., 2019). This is particularly relevant in transdisciplinary approaches, where scholars have highlighted the importance of *unlearning* and *decentring* academic positions to work in transdisciplinary environments (Alonso-Yanez et al., 2019). Thus, when conducting M&E with a variety of stakeholders, priority is not given to a dominant knowledges, nor is M&E expected to occur in a linear fashion (K. A. Waylen, Blackstock, K.L., van Hulst, F.; Damian, C.; Horváth, F.; Johnson, R.; , Kanka, & Rîşnoveanu, 2018), rather it is formative and with a focus on utility (Patton & Campbell-Patton, 2021).

Important in conducting the M&E is exploring the research impact. Measuring research impact is increasingly significant as budgets can't keep up with the growth in research (Reed et al., 2021). Therefore, there is demand to assess what research is most valuable, particularly after the 2008 financial crash (Reed et al., 2021). Professor Mark Reed, author of the Research Impact Handbook, highlighted in a recent co-authored paper, the variety of typologies and frameworks available to evaluate impact. They emphasise the importance of assessing what framework or typology is best suited to a research project, based on the context, whilst also allowing it to be understood by wider audience (Reed et al., 2021). In this research, research impact is understood following the conceptual framework set out by Edwards and Meagher (2020). This framework was chosen because it is used in a UK environmental policy context, forestry policy, but has also been taken up in broader international discussions about impact evaluation (Arnott, Kirchhoff, Meyer, Meadow, & Bednarek, 2020). Moreover, it allows for the post-normal science foundations to this research, set out above, by promoting a formative evaluation approach (Edwards & Meagher, 2020).

Edwards and Meagher's (2020) framework was developed to move away from logic models or logical frameworks, particularly popular in international development. They argue that logic models and frameworks too easily imply a linear causality critiqued above, connecting awareness raising to behavioural change, whilst conversely often overcomplicating, which limits their accessibility (Edwards & Meagher, 2020). They follow the lead of existing literature (Fazey et al., 2014) to move from knowledge transfer to knowledge exchange. Thus, they focus their framework on 'understanding, reflection, improvement and communication' (Edwards & Meagher, 2020: 2). Central to the approach in this research are the five foci of impact set out in the framework. These five impact foci are:

- Instrumental, for example changes to policies etc.
- Conceptual, for example changes to knowledge etc.
- Capacity-building, for example changes to skill and expertise etc.
- Enduring connectivity, for example changes to relationships etc.

- Culture/attitudes towards knowledge exchange and the research (Edwards & Meagher, 2020)

The framework goes further to explore who is impacted, such as policy makers or communities, and what caused the impact, such as research outputs or disseminations etc. Exploring impact through this conceptual framework allows researchers to improve accountability, reputations, the quality of their research and the societal benefits of the research. It is acknowledged in the literature that these impacts may be hard to measure and may not occur directly after research (Matthews et al., 2011; McIntosh et al., 2011). However, it is important to attempt to assess different forms of outcomes from the research working collaboratively with the participants (Blackstock, Kelly, & Horsey, 2007; McIntosh et al., 2011). Whilst the research takes a non-linear approach to M&E it does recognise the need to follow a robust theory and clear framework, with some form of baseline agreed upon (Morris, Blackstock, Hastings, & Towers, 2012).

To this end, the research also takes a Utilisation Focused Evaluation approach, which was influential in the forming of Edwards and Meagher's (2020) impact framework. A Utilisation Focused Evaluation Approach was developed by Michael Quinn Patton, who builds on blue marble evaluation (considering global systems) and developmental evaluation (considering emergent patterns) to focus on the utility of the research and evaluation (Patton & Campbell-Patton, 2021). This assists researchers and participants in learning and improving future policy (Patton & Campbell-Patton, 2021).

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